

False Memories

The Mandela Effect? Have you ever sworn something happened only to find out it never existed?

Have you ever sworn someone said something verbatim, but they never did?

It's your memory, you saw it happen, you heard it happen, You are confident in what you saw, you witnessed it first-hand. Until you realise even your own brain fools you.

Why is your own mind lying to you?

Why can't your own mind give you the safety you crave?

What if you've been simply lying to yourself all along?

What If your memory was just a false witness?

Why are you deceiving yourself?

***“Memory’s malleability is both its curse and its salvation.”
— Daniel L. Schacter***

For the lot of us, I know having fake memories might be a vivid or distant concept. Regardless of whether you'd consider yourself to be an individual with bad memory, we have this tendency to be confident in the memories you witnessed and have collected.

But how and why exactly do we unconsciously create something that never happened?

How does our brain work without our control?

How does it form thoughts without our awareness?

I will now be putting you in the shoes of a detective to figure this out.

Look at the image given below:

you are the eye-witness,
That is the criminal
Give yourself 30 seconds to look at the criminal

Above are the suspects, using your eye-witness abilities.

Which one of the above suspects was the perpetrator in the picture you just saw?

If you picked G, you're wrong
If you picked C, you're wrong
If you picked D, you're wrong again
Infact, if you picked anyone at all from the above suspects, you're wrong.

None of the above suspects was the actual perpetrator, meaning that if you picked an individual from the above image, you have falsely accused an innocent person of having committed a crime.

Though this case was entirely fictional and AI-generated, it is an estimated, close-to- accurate representation of eyewitness-misidentification which is the leading cause of miscarriages of justice at 75%

The reason you might've committed errors is simply because of the framing of the question
"Which one of the above suspects is the criminal" urges you to pick one of the above suspects that more closely resembles your memory. Had I, instead, asked,
"Which one of the above suspects do you think is the criminal according to your memory, they may or may not be in the above list" would urge you to re-evaluate your memory and forfeit on actually choosing one.

This can also be demonstrated by an experiment conducted by Elizabeth F. Loftus & John C. Palmer (1974) called the "Reconstruction of Automobile Destruction

The experimenters showed participants crash-crash videos after which they were asked to estimate the speed at which the cars crashed into each other.

However, when asking the participants questions, they divided them by using different verbs. For example:

“At what speed did the cars **hit** each other”

Or

“At what speed did the cars **smash** into each other”

“At what speed did the cars **crash** into each other”

“At what speed did the cars come into **contact** with each other”

Results showed that participants who were asked the question using verbs such as “Smash” or “crash” were more likely to estimate higher speeds.

The experiments also added a follow up question asking if there was any broken glass. Although there wasn't any in the videos, participants who received the word “smash” or “crash” recalled seeing broken glass.

This serves as striking evidence to prove that the framing of questions along with the vocabulary used can significantly impact memory and form confabulation

This experiment was precisely conducted to prove that

language used in eyewitness testimony can alter memory.

This means that human memory isn't like a storagebox, or a video-recorder, but is instead, reconstructive in nature. Meaning it can be easily mixed up with imagination and suggestion based on the structure of questions and condition of the environment(eg: stressful environments, post-trauma state etc)

The Innocence project is an active program created to tackle this, However, inspite of several actions taken including S.B. 141 reforms. Eye-witness misidentification persists in it's misfortune imprisoning the innocent, and liberalising the guilty.